

STUDIES ON GUM JEOL (*ODINA WODIER*, ROXB.). PART III. THE ALDOBIONIC ACID

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The jeolic acid isolated from gum jeol has been hydrolysed further by H_2SO_4 (conc. $\approx 1N$) and the aldobionic acid, so formed, has been further hydrolysed by prolonged refluxing with H_2SO_4 (conc. $> 1.5N$) and the products identified as *d*-galactose and galacturonic acid.

In Part II of this series (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1945, 25, 63) it has been shown that the gum on mild hydrolysis yields some sugar and a complex acid which forms colloidal solution in water. This complex acid (termed "jeolic acid" in these investigations) has been further broken up by acids on continued refluxing to yield some more sugars. The sugars, thus obtained from hydrolysis of gum jeol, have been characterised as *l*-arabinose and *d*-galactose mainly.

Hydrolysis of the complex jeolic acid has been shown to yield, besides the sugar mentioned above, an acid which it is the aim of the present investigation to prepare in a pure state and characterise. Recent work on the constitution of the arabic acid from gum arabic has shown that it is a compound of glycuronic acid with *d*-galactose to which other carbohydrate groups remain bound by glycosidic binding (Butler and Cretcher, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1929, 51, 1519; Norman, *Biochem. J.*, 1929, 23, 24, 524). In fact Weinmann (*Ber.*, 1929, 62, 1639) evolved a complete method of preparing this *d*-glycuronic acid in considerable quantities from the gum and has thus lent support to the above views regarding its constitution. This acid kernel to which other carbohydrate groups are attached in the gum is looked upon by all these workers as galactose-glycuronic acid and it has been more thoroughly studied by Heidelberger and Kendall (*J. Biol. Chem.*, 1929, 84, 629). Haworth (*Ber.*, 1932, 65, 43) has shown that this acid kernel of the gum, commonly known as the aldobionic acid, is a compound of the reduced galactose group in position 6 with glycuronic acid (cf. Hotchkins and Goebel, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.* 1936, 58, 358).

Work on a similar line has been taken up in the present case.

EXPERIMENTAL

Preparation of Calcium Aldobionate.—The method followed was essentially that of Heidelberger, Avery and Goebel (*J. Expt. Med.*, 1929, 49, 847) with modifications in several stages wherever found essential.

About 200 g. of gum jeol, purified by precipitation with alcohol (*vide* Part I of this series, *this Journal*, 1948, 25, 59) and dried in air, were directly dissolved in 2 litres of $N-H_2SO_4$ and refluxed for $\frac{1}{2}$ hour on the asbestos board. The concentration of H_2SO_4 and the period of refluxing were found to be sufficient for the hydrolysis of the gum to its

aldobionic acid stage, as it roughly produced the expected amount of reducing sugars (about 83%). After removal of H_2SO_4 quantitatively by $Ba(OH)_2$, the solution obtained after filtration (deep yellow colour) was concentrated to about 300 c.c. under reduced pressure, when the colour deepened. It was then heated with $CaCO_3$ (to convert the acid, if any, into its Ca salt) and animal charcoal on the water-bath for $\frac{1}{2}$ hour and filtered. The colour still persisted. The solution was further concentrated to 100 c.c. whereby the colour became deeper. It was poured into 1000 c.c. of methyl alcohol (free from acetone) when a light yellow precipitate of the Ca salt separated out which was filtered. During filtration the precipitate turned brown and became sticky. Methyl alcohol was then removed from the Ca salt by heating it over an asbestos board on a low flame, when the precipitate changed to a spongy mass. About 18 g. of the crude calcium salt were thus obtained.

Purification.—The salt, thus obtained, was dissolved in water, boiled with animal charcoal, and filtered. The filtrate was poured into 10 times its volume of methyl alcohol and the precipitate filtered again. This process was repeated thrice when the salt showed no tendency to change its physical appearance as noted above. The yield on the dry basis was about 5.5 g. The colour of the aqueous solution of this salt was light yellow. Exactly 0.2052 g. of this Ca salt gave on analysis 0.0198 g. of CaO on ignition wherefrom Ca amounted to 5.8% of the original salt. Assuming the formation of a similar acid as the aldobionic acid from gum arabic by the combination of a molecule of hexuronic acid with a hexose and calculating for $(C_{12}H_{18}O_{12})_2Ca$, the percentage of Ca should be 5.33. The present salt thus shows a high percentage of Ca. On further purification the figure came down to 5.78% of Ca. This high percentage might also be due to the formation of some calcium uronate by further decomposition of the acid by hydrolysis (cf. Heidelberg, Avery and Goebel, *loc. cit.*).

The Cinchonidine Salt.—The above salt (5 g.), which was mostly Ca aldobionate, was treated with the theoretical amount of oxalic acid in solution and Ca oxalate was removed by filtration. The filtrate containing the free acid (aldobionic) was treated with alcoholic solution of cinchonidine containing just the equivalent amount of base in it. The alcohol was removed under reduced pressure. A small quantity of cinchonidine that remained behind was filtered off and the solution concentrated *in vacuo*. In the case of cinchonidine salt of aldobionic acid from gum arabic, Heidelberg and Kendall (*loc. cit.*) observed a spontaneous separation of the salt under similar conditions. This point was carefully observed in all the three different samples of the cinchonidine salt prepared in this connection but every time it was found that the cinchonidine salt, if formed, remained in solution and did not separate on concentration. This suggests that the cinchonidine salts, and therefore the aldobionic acids from the two gums, might be different from each other.

However, the concentrated solution of the cinchonidine salt was reddish in colour and fairly viscous. The solution was kept at 0° for about 3 days in a refrigerator but no crystal was found to separate out. The solution was then kept immersed in a freezing mixture when crystals were observed to come down in an hour's time. Attempt was made to separate these crystals by filtration in a funnel kept cool in the freezing mixture but crystals melted as soon as they approached the room temperature. Owing to such

difficulties crystallisation by acetone was tried but a gummy precipitate came down. This gummy mass was dissolved in water and allowed to crystallise but to no effect. Attempts at crystallisation of the cinchonidine salt were therefore abandoned and the solution was evaporated to dryness slowly under reduced pressure when an amorphous brown mass melting within $150-160^{\circ}$ was obtained (Heidelberger and Goebel, gives m. p. 172° , *J. Exp. Med.*, 1929, **49**, 854).

Isolation of the Acid.—The amorphous cinchonidine salt was dissolved in water and cinchonidine removed by treatment with baryta till neutral to phenolphthalein and filtered. Barium was then removed by H_2SO_4 quantitatively and the solution concentrated in *vacuo*. A slight flocculent mass was observed to come out on concentration; it was filtered off and the filtrate further concentrated in *vacuo* till the residue swelled up to a spongy mass. The residue was dissolved in minimum amount of water, and acetone added till turbidity was perceptible. No crystals were obtained.

This failure to obtain crystals of aldobionic acid or its cinchonidine salt by the same method, which was successful in the case of gum arabic, further suggests a fundamental difference between the acids obtained from the two gums.

It was therefore thought desirable to prepare the amorphous acid and then to purify the sample as far as practicable. Obviously it was found useless to proceed through the cinchonidine salt. The purified calcium salt (4 g.) from a previous operation, mentioned above, was quantitatively treated with oxalic acid to remove calcium. The aldobionic acid was then removed from the solution by evaporation to dryness in *vacuo*, the residue being extracted with 700 c.c. of methyl alcohol. The salt appeared to be sparingly soluble in methyl alcohol (cf. the corresponding acid derived from arabic acid). The methyl alcoholic solution was evaporated under reduced pressure to 100 c.c. when a white flocculent precipitate was obtained. The remaining solution after removal of this precipitate was concentrated in vacuum at the room temperature since the substance tended to charring at higher temperatures. When the solution was highly concentrated and presented a viscous appearance, solids began to make their appearance on the sides of the vessel. On further concentration needle-shaped crystals were obtained. But the crystals could not be recovered since, when the methyl alcohol was completely removed, the crystals turned into a spongy mass which could be easily broken and scraped out from the vessel. The amount obtained was 0.4 g. from 4 g. of Ca salt. It was orange in colour and if kept for some time, it turned sticky and brown in colour. After about 24 hours the mass became hard and brittle. The amorphous acid (0.3619 g.) was dissolved in 200 c.c. of water and its rotation observed in a dm. tube amounted to $+0.18^{\circ}$. $[\alpha]_D^{27} = +99^{\circ}.45$. (Found: C, 40.40; H, 5.61; O, 53.90. $C_{12}H_{26}O_{12}$ requires C, 40.45; H, 5.62; O, 53.93 per cent).

Identification of the Aldobionic Acid.—The aldobionic acid, thus obtained, appears to have a formula $C_{12}H_{26}O_{12}$ which is identical with that obtained by Heidelberger *et al* (*loc.cit.*) from gum arabic, and which has been identified by them to be galactose-glycuronic acid. In the present case the acid obtained differs in many respects in point of solubility etc. from the latter and it appears that although they might have identical formula they are still fundamentally different. For this reason the present aldobionic acid was further

hydrolysed into its constituent acid and sugar, if there be any, and the constituents identified and characterised.

(i). *Uronic Acid.*—The impure aldobionic acid (5 g.), obtained by removal of Ca from the crude calcium aldobionate (5 g.) was refluxed with H_2SO_4 (about 1.5 N) for about 20 hours and the excess of H_2SO_4 removed by $Ba(OH)_2$ quantitatively. The acid was then converted into its Ba salt by further addition of $Ba(OH)_2$ till neutral by test with phenolphthalein. The solution was then poured into 5 times its volume of 98% alcohol when a white precipitate came down. The precipitate was filtered and was observed to change to a brown colour and became sticky on keeping. The filtrate still contained some Ba salt dispersed in solution which settled in about 72 hours at the room temperature (28-29°). The Ba salt thus collected was then purified by dissolution in minimum quantity of water and precipitation twice by alcohol. Ba was then quantitatively removed by H_2SO_4 and the filtrate obtained by separation of $BaSO_4$ was poured into twice its volume of alcohol. From analysis of an aliquot part of this solution necessary amount of cinchonidine, equivalent to the acid present, was added, and the solution evaporated *in vacuo* to about 7 or 8 c.c., when small needle-shaped crystals separated out. On keeping for 24 hours a good crop of crystals was obtained. Another crop was obtained by further concentration of the mother liquid after separating the first crop. The crystals obtained in two crops were then dissolved in absolute alcohol and boiled slowly on a water-bath with animal charcoal to remove the colour. After removal of charcoal by filtration sufficient water was added to render the concentration of alcohol 75% by volume. Needle-shaped crystals then began to appear in about 4 hours' time and a good amount was obtained after about 24 hours. The crystals were again dissolved in alcohol and recrystallised from 75% alcohol. Final yield was about 0.5 g. (about 10%).

The crystals, thus obtained, were believed to be of the cinchonidine salt of the hexuronic acid. It melted sharply at 224° (cinchonidine salt of glycuronic acid melts at 204° and that of the acid obtained from the similar salt from gum arabic melts at 198°, cf. Heidelberg *et al.*, *loc. cit.*). This suggests that the uronic acid obtained from gum jeel might be different from that of gum arabic.

This salt was hydrolysed by addition of $Ba(OH)_2$ to separate the cinchonidine and to form a Ba salt which was subsequently treated with H_2SO_4 to remove all barium. After filtering off the $BaSO_4$, the solution was evaporated to a small bulk under reduced pressure. A small quantity of the acid separating in the solid state was first tested with Tollen's reagent when a red coloration indicated the presence of uronic acid and/or a pentose sugar. The m.p. of the substance was observed to be 160.5° and its $[\alpha]_D^{20}$ (observed in 1% aqueous solution) was +57°.2 (m.p. of *d*-galacturonic acid is 159° and its $[\alpha]_D = +55.6$, vide Thorpe, "Dictionary of Applied Chemistry," Vol II, p. 297). (Found: C, 36.9; H, 5.2; O, 57.9. Calc. for *d*-galacturonic acid: C, 37.1; H, 5.15; O, 57.73 per cent).

The acid was then oxidised by HNO_3 (1:1) to convert it into a dibasic acid, if possible. The acid so obtained presented a crystalline appearance of mucic acid melting sharply at 216° (m.p. of mucic acid, 218°). It was further confirmed by converting it into the tetraacetyl derivative (vide Part II of this series, *loc. cit.*) which melted at 262° (m.p. of the tetraacetyl derivative of mucic acid, 266°). The dibasic acid was further confirmed by

a negative test (that it was not saccharic acid) by converting it into the potassium salt which was found to be soluble. An insoluble salt would have indicated the existence of saccharic acid. The uronic acid from the gum thus appears to be *d*-galacturonic acid (contrast the glycuronic acid obtained from gum arabic).

(ii). *The sugar*.—The filtrate, obtained after separation of the Ba salt of the hexuronic acid by alcohol contained some sugar as suspected from its reducing properties. The sugar was recovered by evaporation in *vacuo*. It was then taken up in a small amount of hot glacial acetic acid and filtered. The sugar crystallised on cooling and recrystallised twice from methyl alcohol. The yield was about 0.3 g.* The sugar was not a pentose as it did not respond to the furfural test. It was therefore believed to be a hexose and confirmed by combustion experiments. (Found: C, 39.8; H, 6.8; O, 53.4. Calc. for $C_6H_{12}O_6$: C, 40; H, 6.67; O, 53.3 per cent).

The sugar melted at 168° (m.p. of *d*-galactose, 166°) and showed a specific rotation, $[\alpha]_D^{20} = +82$, while $[\alpha]_D^{20}$ for *d*-galactose was found to be +80°. The mixed melting point with *d*-galactose was observed to be sharply at 166°. Confirmatory tests were performed on the suspected *d*-galactose by conversion into its dibasic acid by treatment with HNO_3 (1:1). The crystals of the dibasic acid presented peculiarities of mucic acid in appearance and an almost identical m.p. of 214°. Further confirmation was made by converting the mucic acid into its tetraacetyl derivative and noting its m.p. (264°). The sugar thus definitely appears to be *d*-galactose.

CONCLUSIONS

Drastic hydrolysis of gum jeol with H_2SO_4 (about 1*N*) yields an aldobionic acid which has been isolated, purified and characterised.

The aldobionic acid decomposes on hydrolysis with H_2SO_4 (1.5 *N* approx.) and yields a hexuronic acid which has been identified with galacturonic acid and a sugar which has been confirmed to be *d*-galactose.

The aldobionic acid from gum jeol is thus galactose-galacturonic acid (cf. galactose-glycuronic acid from gum arabic).

The difference between gum arabic and gum jeol thus appears to be more fundamental than what it appears at the first sight. The differences in solubility or physical appearance are probably outward manifestations of an intrinsic difference of a more fundamental type. Gum jeol appears from the percentage of sugar obtained from it to be more complex than gum arabic. While the complex acid (jeolic acid) can be obtained from

* The same amount of aldobionic acid yielded about 0.5 g. of the hexuronic acid. Assuming that the aldobionic acid is formed by combination of hexuronic acid with a hexose in molecular proportion, 0.5 g. of the uronic acid would combine with 0.45 g. of hexose, 0.3 g., obtained above is thus too small but it may be due to the incomplete separation of the sugar.

gum jeol by mild hydrolysis with H_2SO_4 (0.5 *N*) that of gum arabic is more easily obtained by the mere removal of the basic radicals present in the gum (Part II of the series, *loc. cit.*). This aspect will be taken up again in the next part (Part IV) in connection with the electrodialysis of both the gum solutions.

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